

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

D3.2 Report on Surrogate Models in the Case Studies

VERSION 4

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

This deliverable, namely D3.2, summarizes the activities carried out in Task 3.2 “Training and Validation of the Models in the Case Studies” (Lead: UNIPR/ participants: UPV, UFZ, TUC, IST-ID, CERTE and BU). The aim of D3.2 is to outline the surrogate models implemented for each study case. Their evaluation and performance are discussed. Two types of smart models were developed: the first type is developed based on long-time historical data, the so-called data-driven models; the second one is built on the basis of available numerical model. For each pilot site, the objectives of the surrogate model, the description of the complete numerical model or available data, the description of the surrogate model and the evaluation of the performance are presented.

1. Introduction

InTheMED focuses on the development of new simplified smart models that allow analysing alternative scenarios and making decisions under uncertain future conditions with small computational effort. Numerical models are crucial for the description of groundwater processes and the configuration of management scenarios. However, they need the knowledge of several factors that are often difficult to quantify and they require a large computation time to be run. The surrogate models aim to replace the numerical models allowing to perform several quick evaluations of the groundwater condition under different scenarios. These new models are built on the basis of long-time historical data and/or detailed numerical models with the aim to provide specific answers tailored to the stakeholder needs.

For each case study, a specific surrogate model addressing the particular problem of the site is built. For Requena-Utiel (Spain), Konya (Turkey) and Tympaki (Greece), surrogate models based on the results of complete numerical models have been developed. The first and second case study use machine learning algorithms, in particular, Random Forest and Artificial Neural Network. The third one is a spatiotemporal geostatistical model. For Grombalia (Tunisia) and Castro Verde (Portugal), the numerical models are not available and data-driven surrogate models were developed using a statistical approach that aims to use regression models to assess the impact of the climate change on the groundwater level.

The smart and calibrated models will be used in Task 3.4 to analyse the effects of climate change and hypothetical scenarios of socio-economic activities that may induce a change in groundwater resources. Impacts of the anthropogenic actions cannot be considered in the surrogate models developed for Grombalia (Tunisia) and Castro Verde (Portugal).

2. Case Studies

2.1. Requena-Utiel

Objectives of the Surrogate Model

In the Requena-Utiel aquifer, Spain, there is a problem with the continuous decline of piezometric heads in the aquifer, which may worsen due to the effects of climate change. In that situation, numerical models are fundamental for the determination of best management scenarios; however, their configuration, build and run require large computational time in addition to specialized knowledge. The surrogate model implemented here will replace the numerical models with a quick, easy-to-use, reliable tool. Such a tool will be used to analyse the impact of future climate scenarios and groundwater use in the piezometric heads.

Description of the Complete Numerical Model

The model domain consists of two groundwater aquifers, Requena-Utiel and Cabrillas-Malacara, which are delimited by the Water Framework Directive and the Júcar Basin authority as basic management units. Here the two aquifers were considered together due to the relevance of their hydraulic connection and from here on we refer to both just as Requena-Utiel aquifer.

The model domain is discretized into a regular mesh of square cells of 500 x 500 m² made up of 127 columns, 99 rows and 3 layers that rest on an impermeable bed of Keuper facies. The upper aquifer is quaternary, free and composed of detrital materials from the alluvial of the Magro River and glacia from the Utiel mountains. The lower aquifer is a Miocene aquifer divided into two systems. The upper system is a calcareous Miocene aquifer, free and composed of Pontian limestone and the lower system is a base conglomerate Miocene aquifer. It behaves as a confined or semi-confined aquifer, depending on the site. It is composed of alternating levels of conglomerates and sandstones with clayey sections and conglomerates of the tertiary formation.

The lateral limits correspond to the interactions between the aquifers under study and the adjacent ones. In the north, there is the Mira aquifer, and there is an estimated flux towards the Requena-Utiel aquifer of 11 hm³/year. In the southeast, there is an estimated flux from

Requena-Utiel to Buñol-Cheste of 24 hm³/year. Based on piezometers located around the studied aquifer and on the estimated flux, the conductance values were calibrated, and the head-dependent flux boundaries were defined to be used in the north and southeast boundaries. The rest of the limits are considered impermeable. Figure 1 shows the studied aquifer and its lateral limits.

Figure 1. Requena-Utiel aquifer and its lateral limits

It was considered as internal boundary conditions the Magro, the Madre and the Buñol rivers and the Torre ravine, as well as the recharge by infiltration of precipitation and by irrigation and pumping wells. The Magro river crosses the study area through the central part from the northeast to the southeast and it is the one that has the most significant influence on the aquifer. The Madre river is located in the northwest, the Torre ravine is in the northeast, and the Buñol river is in the southeast. A third type boundary condition was used to represent the rivers and after a calibration process, a conductance of 100 m²/day was defined for the Torre ravine and the Madre river, to the Magro and Buñol rivers, a conductance of 12 and 2.5 m²/day were defined, respectively.

The second type boundary condition was used to represent both the recharge and the pumping well. The recharge was considered heterogeneous in space by dividing the study area into 15 recharge zones based on the PATRICAL model (Pérez-Martín, M.A., 2005), and time, by following the dry and rainy seasons of the hydrological year. The pumping from wells was also considered variable in space and time, according to data available from the Júcar Basin authority.

Regions of similar hydrogeological behaviour have been defined for the spatial characterization of the hydrogeological parameters, resulting in five different domains. In the same way, these five domains have been thoroughly subdivided to create 20 subdomains. The value of hydraulic conductivity has a range between 0.02 and 19.5 m/day. Specific yield has a range between 0.0001 and 0.05, while specific storage varies between 0.3 and 0.1 m^{-1} .

The numerical model performs a transient simulation during the period between the years of 1980 and 2016, with a monthly time discretization. The initial condition was defined from a previous steady-state simulation, representing the aquifer state from 1940 to 1979.

The numerical problem was solved by using the code MODFLOW 2005 (Harbaugh, A.W., 2005) through FloPy (Bakker et al., 2016).

The calibration was performed by adjusting model parameters manually and evaluating the difference between observed and simulated piezometric heads at ten measurement locations where time-series data were available.

Description of the Surrogate Model

The idea is to use a machine learning algorithm to capture relationships between the piezometric heads in the monitoring points (targets) and the scenarios evaluated (features). The smart modelling process implemented can be summarized in six steps as follows:

The first step is to generate the data that will feed the algorithm to be trained. We selected 110 points along the study area, so that the entire aquifer was covered. These points were used as monitoring point of the piezometric head, then 110 targets were defined. The year, month, recharge, and pumping rate were selected as features. Since the basic numerical model previously described was built and satisfactorily calibrated, it served as a base for generating a

training dataset. For that, we kept all the model characteristics constant except recharge and pumping rate. The recharge rate was assumed to have an increment and a reduction of 30% (represented by a recharge factor ranging from 0.70 to 1.3) in relation to the average of the last ten years. It was assumed that the change in the recharge rate follows a linear function (increasing or decreasing) in time, with zero change for the first time-step (# 0) and a maximum change for the last time-step (# 432). Pumping wells were considered to have an increment and a reduction of 25% in relation to the average of the last ten years and it is applied directly to each time-step. It was generated 64 combinations of recharge and pumping rate. After that, the numerical model was performed for each combination between 2016 and 2052 (36 years), with a monthly time discretization (totalling 432 months), and the values of the piezometric heads were computed in the 110 monitoring points. In summary, for each model run, we obtained a dataset of 432 values of piezometric head, totalling a dataset with 27,648 data for each monitoring point. Figure 2 shows part of the generated dataset.

month	year	recharge	pumping	obs_point 1	obs_point 2	obs_point 3	obs_point 4	obs_point 5	obs_point 6	obs_point 7	obs_point 8	obs_point 9	obs_point 10
10	2016	0.7	0.75	731.17	766.29	728.46	773.34	748.91	733.35	735.34	783.12	768.91	755.51
11	2016	0.7	0.75	731.18	766.30	728.46	773.33	748.91	733.61	735.87	783.12	768.91	755.56
12	2016	0.7	0.75	731.19	766.31	728.46	773.33	748.91	733.56	735.94	783.11	768.91	755.57
1	2017	0.7	0.75	731.20	766.31	728.46	773.32	748.91	733.64	736.18	783.11	768.91	755.61
2	2017	0.7	0.75	731.20	766.32	728.46	773.32	748.91	733.62	736.25	783.10	768.91	755.63
3	2017	0.7	0.75	731.21	766.33	728.46	773.32	748.90	734.13	737.25	783.11	768.91	755.71
4	2017	0.7	0.75	731.22	766.34	728.46	773.32	748.90	734.27	737.82	783.10	768.91	755.73
5	2017	0.7	0.75	731.23	766.35	728.47	773.32	748.90	734.06	737.77	783.10	768.91	755.72
6	2017	0.7	0.75	731.23	766.36	728.47	773.32	748.90	733.77	737.40	783.09	768.91	755.71
7	2017	0.7	0.75	731.24	766.36	728.47	773.32	748.89	733.48	736.86	783.07	768.91	755.69
8	2017	0.7	0.75	731.25	766.37	728.47	773.32	748.89	733.28	736.36	783.07	768.91	755.69
9	2017	0.7	0.75	731.26	766.37	728.47	773.31	748.89	733.36	736.31	783.06	768.91	755.71
10	2017	0.7	0.75	731.26	766.38	728.47	773.31	748.88	733.70	736.82	783.06	768.91	755.75
11	2017	0.7	0.75	731.27	766.39	728.47	773.31	748.88	733.89	737.26	783.06	768.91	755.77
12	2017	0.7	0.75	731.28	766.39	728.47	773.31	748.88	733.80	737.25	783.05	768.91	755.76
1	2018	0.7	0.75	731.29	766.40	728.48	773.32	748.88	733.84	737.40	783.04	768.91	755.77
2	2018	0.7	0.75	731.29	766.41	728.48	773.32	748.87	733.80	737.40	783.04	768.91	755.77
3	2018	0.7	0.75	731.30	766.42	728.48	773.32	748.87	734.28	738.31	783.04	768.91	755.82
4	2018	0.7	0.75	731.31	766.43	728.48	773.33	748.87	734.41	738.82	783.04	768.91	755.83
5	2018	0.7	0.75	731.32	766.43	728.48	773.33	748.87	734.18	738.70	783.03	768.91	755.80
6	2018	0.7	0.75	731.32	766.44	728.48	773.33	748.87	733.89	738.27	783.02	768.91	755.78
7	2018	0.7	0.75	731.33	766.45	728.48	773.33	748.86	733.59	737.68	783.01	768.91	755.75
8	2018	0.7	0.75	731.34	766.45	728.48	773.33	748.86	733.38	737.13	783.00	768.91	755.73

Figure 2. Part of the generated dataset used for training the surrogate model

The second step is to define the best random split of the data set into training and test data, which will be used to evaluate the performance of the model. In our case, the best training and test results were obtained from 90% training and 10% test data.

The third step is to define a suitable algorithm and its hyperparameters. We have tested the performance obtained with AdaBoost (Freund & Schapire, 1997), XGBoost (Chen & Guestrin, 2016) and Random Forest regression (Breiman, 2001). Despite all of them being ensemble

methods, only Random Forest is natively multi-output, as required in our problem, so AdaBoost and XGBoost were adapted to handle multi-output regression problems. After comparing the performance of the tree aforementioned algorithms, we selected the latter, which is a supervised machine learning algorithm for building a predictor ensemble with a set of decision trees (forest) that grow in randomly selected sub-samples of the dataset (Biau, 2012; Breiman, 2001; Cutler et al., 2012).

By using the scikit-learn library in Python (Python Core Team, 2015), it was conducted a sensitivity analysis to define the best hyperparameters to be used in the Random Forest regressor: the number of trees in the forest = 60, the maximum depth of the tree = 30, the minimum number of samples required to split an internal node = 2, the number of features to consider = 0.75. We used the default values of all other hyperparameters as defined in scikit-learn.

The fourth step is to train the regressor by feeding it with 90% of the dataset generated in the first step: a data set with 24,883 data.

In the fifth step, the performance of the fully trained surrogate model is evaluated on the testing dataset previously defined in step 2. Additionally, k-fold cross-validation with $k = 5$ is also performed to evaluate the model on a limited data sample.

Finally, in the sixth step, the regressor is used to predict. The user must provide as input data: month, year, change in the recharge (increase or reduction), and change in the pumping rate (increase or reduction). As a result, the model will return the interpolated piezometric head for the entire aquifer based on the 110 monitoring points. The interpolation was done in Python by using the radial basis function method with the thin plate spline method.

Evaluation of the Performance

The performance of the surrogate model was obtained by evaluating the regression score and the mean square error for testing data. Cross-validation was also performed as an alternative method to estimate the model skill. As the surrogate model is used to replace the numerical model due to its high computational cost, it is also important here to evaluate the time needed to obtain a response when using the numerical or the surrogate models. Figure 3a shows the

mean regression score obtained by using Random Forest (RF), AdaBoost (AB) and XGBoost (XB) algorithms, while Figure 3b shows the mean square error over 64 scenarios.

Figure 3a. Mean regression score obtained by using Random Forest (RF), AdaBoost (AB), and XGBoost (XB); Figure 3b. Mean square error over 64 scenarios.

Results shown that Random Forest, AdaBoost, and XGBoost performed similarly and presented high accuracy of the models against the training data. Table 1 shows the results of the cross-validation, and we can see that the good performance is confirmed for the three algorithms.

Table 1. Mean cross-validation scores for each fold

Scores	fold1	fold2	fold3	fold4	fold5
RF	0.86	0.89	0.96	0.93	0.93
AB	0.68	0.81	0.88	0.88	0.79
XB	0.76	0.83	0.91	0.86	0.85

Figure 4 shows the mean CPU time (in seconds) necessary to obtain the response. As mentioned before, Random Forest not only presented high accuracy, as well as the other methods, but also the computational time was reduced in 36 times when compared to the time required by MODFLOW.

Figure 4. Mean CPU time required to calculate and get the piezometric head values

Due to the good performance and computational time obtained by using Random Forest, this is the model chosen to build our surrogate model. Figure 5 shows the piezometric levels obtained with MODFLOW (test data) and with the surrogate model.

Figure 5. Piezometric heads obtained with MODFLOW (test data) and with the surrogate model (Random Forest)

2.2. Tympaki (Greece)

Objectives of the Surrogate Model

The Tympaki area is located on the southern coast of Crete, Greece, and is known for its agricultural production. Due to overpumping, the groundwater level has dropped more than 20 m in the last two decades causing significant problems. To investigate the aquifer, a numerical groundwater model has been implemented using FEFLOW (Diersch, 2005). Then, a surrogate model, based on the full numerical model, has been developed with the aim to simulate groundwater level fluctuations with minimal computational effort and allow evaluation of various climatic and socioeconomic scenarios. In particular, a space-time regression Kriging method acts as surrogate model of the Tympaki aquifer. It is expected that the proposed method can improve the management of groundwater in the basin and satisfy the demands of the relevant management authorities.

Description of the Complete Numerical Model

The study area has a width of about 12.5 km and a length of about 9.1 km. There are 371 pumping wells which were grouped into 20 pumping locations by using the K-nearest neighbors and each group was represented as one pumping well by using the Median Center method, which identifies the location that minimizes the overall Euclidean distance from features in a dataset (Figure 6). The pumping rate of each group is the total pumping rate of all wells constituting the group (expressed in m^3/d). The pumping rates are imported in FEFLOW as time-series with the values being different for the wet and dry seasons.

Figure 6. All pumping wells (small circles) along with the representative ones (big circles) for each group

The discretization of the unconfined aquifer was applied using a triangular finite element mesh, which consists of 11,877 nodes and 15,340 elements. There are two layers and each one of them has 7,670 elements and three slices with 3,959 nodes for each slice. The depth of the model comprises 130 m deep from sea level for the unconfined aquifer. The data for the hydraulic conductivity were extracted from the Decentralized Administration of Crete and they were set for the axis $x'x$ and $y'y$. For $z'z$ the hydraulic conductivity was 10% of the value of $x'x$. The pumping wells as considered in the model are depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Spatial distribution of pumping wells

The calibration – validation process was conducted as follows. In the area of Tympaki, there are 6 observation wells that are distributed in the study area, as shown in Figure 8. The period of the observed hydraulic head data time series is different for each well. The time series period for the precipitation, observation wells and pumping wells are available for the years 2004-2014. For the precipitation, the data of one station is used. In sake of computational time, a mean precipitation was used with a step of 10 days and the input time series is in units of m/d. The data from 04/2004 until 04/2009 are used for calibration and the rest for validation. During the validation period, the field measurements at the observation wells were conducted in random dates so there are periods with no data available at the observation wells. The mean error for the validation period is 6.4 meters.

Figure 8. Observation wells with calibration – validation data available

For the model of the Tympaki area, a first-type flow boundary condition was used along the coastline, where the hydraulic head was set at 0 m. Also, a second-type boundary conditions were set at the north boundaries of the study area. Those boundary conditions are connected to the precipitation so there is a fluctuation to the hydraulic head that is relative to the rainfall. The observation wells that are used in the pumping scenarios were set to monitor the saltwater intrusion zone. As it appears in Figure 9, the intrusion zone is estimated to occur between the coast line and at 5.65 meters above the sea level (at the end of the calibration period), by using the Ghyben – Herzberg relation and considering the depth of the deepest pumping well in the area (226 m below the sea level). The simulation runs are applied for a ten-year period from 01/04/2010 until 31/03/2020, by using the available precipitation data, as well as time series for the pumping rates. For the values of pumping rates obtained from the licences of water use, the results of the model are depicted in Figure 10 and Figure 11 and the values of the hydraulic heads in the observation wells in Figure 12.

Figure 9. Salt water intrusion zone 2009

Figure 10. Simulation results wet period October 2019- March 2020

Figure 11. Simulation results dry period April 2020-September 2020

Figure 12. Simulated hydraulic heads at the observation wells

Description of the Surrogate Model

Spatiotemporal geostatistical analysis of groundwater levels is a significant tool for groundwater resources management. This work presents a valid spatiotemporal geostatistical model for the groundwater level variations of the Tympaki aquifer in Crete, Greece. The main goal of space–time analysis is to model multiple time series of data at spatial locations where a distinct time series is allocated. The time variable is considered an additional dimension in geostatistical prediction. Using spatiotemporal geostatistics, the groundwater level dataset can be usefully exploited in order to identify the spatiotemporal behaviour of the aquifer and to obtain useful information regarding the space–time data correlations for more accurate space–time predictions (Varouchakis 2017; Varouchakis and Hristopulos 2019). The goal of space-time regression kriging (STRK) is to accurately map the aquifer level at variable time-steps using joint space–time information. A space–time experimental variogram is determined from the groundwater level time-series between the hydrological years 2004 and 2015 at 11 sampling stations bi-annually (Figure 13). The experimental spatiotemporal variogram of the fluctuations was successfully fitted by the product–sum model using a Matérn spatial and temporal function. Elevation was considered as a primary auxiliary variable because according to a test provided by Haitjema and Mitchell-Bruker (2005) it was found that it consists a direct replica of the water table. Three more exogenous components in the regression model were considered to investigate their response to the annual monitored groundwater level data. Overall, the following explanatory information were incorporated in the STRK model:

- a) elevation at each well location from a Digital elevation model
- b) mean annual monitored rainfall trend for a specific period through an exponentially-weighted-moving-average (EWMA) filter (Varouchakis and Hristopulos 2019) in order to incorporate the effect of the projected climate change scenarios. The available monitored rainfall variability in the area from the three rainfall stations is described in detail in deliverable 5.1 Report on site characterization and hot spot identification (Akrouf et al. 2021).
- c) spatial average of groundwater level in the area from monitoring wells.
- d) spatial average of the agreed pumping rates at the pumping wells operating in the area.

The output of the STRK model is the prediction of annual groundwater level variations at 53 monitoring locations and in a 50x50 grid of the case study area under the overall effect of different scenarios. The scenarios consider potential changes in spatial average groundwater levels and spatial average pumping rates as auxiliary information in the regression component of the STRK model, taking into account the availability of surface water from a reservoir operation in the area (Varouchakis et al., 2022). Following the STRK model validation, the proposed surrogate model can be applied to obtain forecasts of groundwater conditions considering also future climate scenarios.

Figure 13. Space–time variogram fit (stars) using the product–sum model

The complete application steps for the surrogate model are summarized below:

Step 1: Data processing:

a) Annual groundwater level data at 11 wells for the period 2004-2020; b) Digital elevation map; c) spatial annual rainfall from three stations for the period 2004-2020; d) spatial average of licensed pumping rates; e) spatial average of groundwater level for the reference period 2019-2020.

It is noteworthy that the Self Organization Maps (SOM) approach can be used to enhance the performance of the surrogate model by selecting the appropriate monitoring wells and pumping wells to increase the prediction capability of the STRK.

Step 2: STRK model:

- a) Exponentially-weighted-moving-average filter of monitored temporal rainfall variability.
- b) Regression model among monitored annual groundwater level at each well and, local elevation, filtered rainfall variability, spatial average pumping and spatial average groundwater level of the reference years.
- c) Calculation of residuals; space-time (ST) experimental variogram calculation of residuals and ST theoretical variogram fit to define the spatiotemporal dependence. The determined ST product-sum variogram parameters remain constant for projection scenarios.
- d) Prediction of residual groundwater level at 53 monitoring wells and at ungauged grid locations (50x50) of the area using STOK estimator during the period 2021-2039 considering the prior dynamic aquifer level variability.
- e) Application of the global regression model at each location specified in step (d) for the period 2021-2039 using the calculated parameters, elevation at each location, rainfall input from the EWMA model using the mean of the climate change scenarios, spatial average pumping and spatial average groundwater level according to the applied coefficients of the selected management scenario.

Step 3: Final STRK Prediction:

- a) Application of STRK estimator: combination of interpolated residuals (STOK) and regression model estimations at prediction locations (e.g., 53 monitoring wells) to provide the predicted groundwater level.

Evaluation of the Performance

The proposed surrogate model efficiency was assessed by a validation procedure: the STRK was used to predict the bi-annual groundwater level at each sampling station from 2016 to 2020. The cross validation was initially applied for the 11 observation wells. Validation results (Table 2) provided low prediction errors that range from 0.95 to 1.45 m, therefore, maps of groundwater level spatial distribution in the area were developed to assess the aquifer spatiotemporal variability. The predicted groundwater levels contours were compared with those from the numerical model. In addition, a second validation set of groundwater levels was available for the hydrological year 2019-2020 at 53 locations, being 2020 the last modelling

year. These observed groundwater levels came from the registration of private wells during the hydrological year 2019-2020. The cross-validation analysis provided a MAE of 1.75 m. The latter is higher than the one based on the 11 wells for the period 2016-2020 due to the greater spatial distribution of the monitoring points, especially for those close to the boundary zones. However, still the error is satisfactory compared to the range of the groundwater level in the area.

Overall, the surrogate model results based on STRK (Figures 14, 15) agree with those of the numerical model (Figures 10, 11) and they consist a reliable alternative for the modelling of the aquifer levels. The differences between the two modelling approaches are located at the boundary zones due to their different principles on functionality and application. The proposed surrogate model results can be further improved from the enrichment of the available datasets with groundwater level observation locations. This work demonstrated that space–time geostatistics can successfully represent the spatial dynamic behaviour of an aquifer when the space–time dependencies are appropriately modelled, even for a sparse dataset.

Table 2. Average STRK prediction statistical measures for using the product–sum space–time variogram in terms of ME, mean error; MAE, mean absolute error; MARE, mean absolute relative error; RMSE, root mean square error; R^2 , coefficient of determination

	MAE (m)	ME/BIAS (m)	MARE	RMSE (m)	R²
2016	1.10	0.18	0.12	2.75	0.90
2017	0.95	0.08	0.11	2.14	0.91
2018	1.25	-0.25	0.13	3.41	0.88
2019	1.45	-0.32	0.15	3.80	0.88
2020	1.24	0.20	0.13	3.34	0.88

Figure 14. Groundwater level spatial distribution, meters above sea level, for the wet period of October 2019-March 2020

Figure 15. Groundwater level spatial distribution, meters above sea level, for the dry period of April 2020-September 2020

2.3. Konya (Turkey)

Objectives of the Surrogate Model

The Konya closed basin is located in the central Anatolian plateau with an area of about 50,000 km². The surface elevation ranges from about 900 m in the central portions of the basin to 3400 m along the Taurus Mountains which form the southern boundary of the basin (elevation data from General Directorate of Mapping of Turkey) as shown in Figure 16. The basin has a population of about 3.2 million and is characterized by a high level of biodiversity (Yilmaz et al., 2021). The basin has variable climate with Mediterranean climate in the south and dry and cold climate in the north. The mean annual precipitation is about 380 mm, ranging from about 290 mm in the central dry regions to about 650 mm in the southern mountainous boundary of the basin (Figure 17).

Figure 16. Location Map and Surface Elevation of Konya Closed Basin

Figure 17. Average Annual Precipitation of Konya Closed Basin (1970-2020)

The Konya basin is one of the major agricultural regions of Turkey with more than 50% of the plain surface area used for agriculture as shown in the satellite land use map for year of 2018 (Figure 18). With no rivers or streams crossing its boundaries and precipitation concentrated in the winter months, agricultural activities rely heavily on groundwater resources. Despite the semiarid climate of the basin, water-intensive crops are cultivated in large portions of the basin. Especially in the last two decades, there has been a gradual change from traditional wheat farming to more profitable water-demanding crops such as sugar beets and maize (Yilmaz et al., 2021).

Figure 18. Satellite land use map of Konya Closed Basin for year of 2018

As a result of the extensive agricultural activities within the basin, groundwater levels have been steadily declining. This decline has placed significant pressure on the agricultural sector within the basin. To achieve a more sustainable use of groundwater resources in the basin, a hydrogeological model is being developed as part of WP 4 of the InTheMED project. The goal of this model is to estimate the net recharge over the basin which will help in the management of the groundwater resources. The model is also used to assess the impact of different irrigation practices and climate change on the groundwater resources of the basin.

The purpose of the surrogate model is to provide a rapid, efficient and easy to use alternative to the detailed physics-based numerical hydrogeological model. The surrogate model, which is based on the artificial neural network method, will be used to reproduce the spatial historical groundwater head decline in the aquifer and assess the impact of various irrigation and climate change scenarios on the groundwater resources of the basin.

Description of the Complete Numerical Model

UZF Package coupled with MODFLOW-2005 was used to develop a regional model that simulates the unsaturated-saturated groundwater flow over the entire basin. UZF simulates unsaturated flow based on the kinematic wave equation, a simplified version of Richards' equation, whereas MODFLOW simulates three-dimensional finite-difference groundwater flow. Coupling between unsaturated and saturated flow simulation is achieved as follows: for each time step, MODFLOW provides the location of the water table which acts as the lower constant pressure boundary of the UZF model, while the UZF model uses the surface water application (precipitation and irrigation) and evapotranspiration to compute the net recharge into the aquifer (Harbaugh, 2005; Niswonger et al., 2006).

The model domain covers the entire area of the Konya closed basin. No-flow boundary conditions were imposed along the outer model boundaries. Horizontally, the model domain is discretized into 10 km by 10 km uniform square grid (a total of 1015 cells). The initial head data in the model were defined based on the January 2,000 observed groundwater level data. The UZF module solves the kinematic flow equation for each of the model's active cells based on the temporal and spatially variable surface water application and evapotranspiration.

The model simulations extended for a period of 20 years, starting from Jan 1, 2000 to year Jan 1, 2020. The 20-year horizon was divided into 240 monthly stress periods. The time steps used for simulating the groundwater flow was equal to 1 day. Precipitation was determined from 18 meteorological stations covering the entire basin. Monthly precipitation data were defined in the model. Simple kriging was used to estimate the transient precipitation distribution over the entire domain. Figure 19 gives the spatial distribution of the monthly precipitation for selected months/years.

Figure 19. Monthly precipitation distribution over the Konya Closed Basin for selected year/months. Dots show location of available meteorological stations

Soil maps and well logs of the top soil indicate that the soil is mostly silty loam. In the model, the permeability and van Genuchten parameters of the soil are defined based on soil type and direct measurements of the water retention properties of collected soil samples. Geologic maps and well logs developed by the State Hydraulics Works (Devlet Su İşleri, DSI) were used to define the hydraulic conductivity of the aquifer system. DSI carried out a series of pumping tests with drawdown monitored at a total of 78 points. The hydraulic conductivity distribution over the entire domain was estimated using ordinary kriging. Figure 20 shows the spatial distribution of the hydraulic conductivity. The thickness of the aquifer was interpolated based on available well logs. Wherever the bottom of the aquifer was not reached, the bottom elevation was defined equal to the bottom of the well logs.

Figure 20. Hydraulic Conductivity of Konya Closed Basin

Given the large number of unmetered wells in the Konya Plain, it was not possible to directly estimate groundwater extraction rates. For this purpose, irrigation water demand was estimated indirectly from (i) historical crop production for individual townships (TUIK, 2020), (ii) recommended irrigation schedules for the area of Konya for different crops (TAGEM, 2017), (iii) irrigation efficiencies and (iv) land use satellite maps (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service). Historical irrigation efficiencies were defined based on available reports; it is generally observed that enhanced irrigation systems (drip and sprinkle systems) were gradually installed in the Konya plain starting from year 2010. To spatially distribute water demands, groundwater extraction rates for each model grid were defined as the difference between the irrigation water demand within that grid and the actual precipitation. This calculation was performed at monthly basis for the 20-year model duration. Potential evapotranspiration rates were defined based on climate data and land use maps on a monthly basis.

The calibration target was the historical monthly groundwater level data at various monitoring wells covering the entire model domain. The main calibration parameters were the spatial

distribution of the hydraulic conductivity, as well as irrigation efficiency and groundwater extraction rates which are associated with the highest level of uncertainty.

Figure 21 compares the simulated and observed monthly heads at all observation wells; only observation wells with at least 20 years of data are shown. In general, the agreement is good with the simulated water trend close to the observed water ones. The simulated heads also show the seasonal variation in the water level with a sharp drop in summer months followed by gradual increase heads in winter month. Overall, on annual basis, it is observed that the head is dropping throughout the basin with the rate of drop as high as 2 m/year at some wells.

Figure 21. Comparison of the simulated and observed heads

Figure 22 shows the simulated heads at 5-year intervals starting from 2000. The flow is seen to converge towards the north-central part of the basin.

Figure 22. Spatial distribution of the simulated head on January of years 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015 and 2020

Description of the Surrogate Model

The surrogate model is based on an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) able to provide monthly groundwater levels at 30 control points in the domain (Figure 23) for the period (2020-2039), which is discretized in 240 months.

Figure 23. Control Points for Surrogate Model

The ANN consists of interconnected nodes, called neurons, organized into layers. These neurons receive inputs, process them using mathematical operations, and produce outputs. The ANN is designed to learn from data (inputs-targets) and adjust its internal parameters (training phase) to make the network's output align with the target.

In this application, the MATLAB computing environment was utilized for the development of the surrogate model. The ANN is composed by three layers (Figure 24): input (3 neurons), hidden (10 neurons) and output (30 neurons). The hyperbolic tangent was selected as activation function between the input and hidden layers, while the linear activation function was used to process the information between the hidden and output layers. The number of training epochs was set to 50 and the Levenberg-Marquardt learning algorithm was considered for adjusting the network's parameters.

Figure 24. Network design

The ANN utilizes three input features: the precipitation coefficient, the crop coefficient, and the lead time. The precipitation coefficient is applied to the historical rainfall data, while the crop coefficient is applied to the historical water demand data. The lead time indicates the

desired output's timeframe, ranging from 1 to 240 months starting from January 2020. The ANN provides as output the piezometric heads at the 30 control points at the selected lead time.

The first step was to generate the data to train, validate and test the neural network. A dataset of 100 combinations of precipitation and crop coefficients was generated, using the Latin Hypercube Sampling method, assuming a training range of reduction/increase in terms of precipitation equal to +/- 40% (represented by a precipitation coefficient ranging from 0.6 to 1.4) and water demand equal to +/- 25% (represented by a crop coefficient ranging from 0.75 to 1.25). Then, the numerical model was run for each combination in the period 2020 and 2039 (20 years), and the values of the piezometric heads (targets), at the 30 control points, were stored with a monthly time discretization (240 months). In summary, for each model run, we obtained a dataset of 240 values of piezometric heads, totaling a dataset with 24,000 data for each control point.

This dataset was used for training (70%), validating (15%) and testing (15%) the neural network.

The fully trained network can be used to predict groundwater levels at control points inside the training range and will be used to analyze future scenarios that will be discussed in Deliverable 3.4.

Evaluation of the Performance

Figure 25 illustrates the training options and progress of the ANN during the training. The Mean Squared Error (MSE) was selected as reference metric to measure the performance in terms of the average squared difference between the predicted and actual values. The initial value of the training performance is 20.8, and at the end of the learning procedure, it decreases to 0.0067. This denotes the improvement in the network's performance as it undergoes the training process.

Figure 25. Training options and progress

Figure 26 depicts actual values vs model’s prediction. The correlation coefficient, R , is a statistical measure that quantifies the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the target and the output values. It provides a numerical value between -1 and 1, where 1 represents a perfect positive correlation, -1 represents a perfect negative correlation, and 0 represents no correlation. In this specific application, the high correlation coefficient, nearly equal to 1, in all three phases, highlights the excellent performance of the implemented ANN.

Figure 26. Training, validation, test and whole dataset (All) performances of the ANN for the period 2020-2039

2.4. Grombalia (Tunisia)

Objectives of the Surrogate Model

The objective of the surrogate model developed for the Grombalia aquifer is to provide a quick tool to investigate the impact of future climate scenarios on the groundwater resources.

A complete numerical model is not available for this study area; therefore, a data-driven surrogate model has been developed based on groundwater levels, precipitation and temperature data. Assuming that the hydrological processes will not change over time, the proposed method is a statistical method that allows a fast evaluation of groundwater variations based on precipitation and temperature future scenarios.

Description of the Data

The involved study area, shown in Figure 27, is the Grombalia shallow aquifer. The available data are precipitation, temperature, groundwater levels, some quality data and exploitation rate. Among the available data, for their abundance of data, we select precipitations recorded from six gauging stations and temperature from 1 station at a daily scale in the period 1976-2020 (Figure 27 and Table 3). The gaps in the precipitation and temperature time series were filled using the FAO method (Allen et al., 1998). For temperature data, the gaps were filled using the temperature data provided by the WATCH Forcing dataset (WFD; Weedon et al., 2010), which is a twentieth century meteorological forcing dataset that covers from 1958 to 2001 with 0.5 x 0.5 degrees spatial resolution. The WFD temperature records at the four cells closest to the gauging station are analysed and the more correlated with the observed time-series was used to fill the gaps according to the FAO method. The precipitation data have been processed with the Thiessen polygon techniques to obtain precipitation areal averages. Instead, the areal temperature was considered equal to that recorded in the only available station. The climate variables are investigated in terms of Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Indices (SPEIs) computed at different accumulation periods (3, 6, 9, 12, 18, 24 and 36 months). The SPEI is a statistical index useful in detecting the meteorological droughts using monthly differences between precipitation and potential evapotranspiration; (Vicente-Serrano et al. 2010). Figure 28 reports the SPEI computed considering the precipitation and temperature data averaged over the area of interest. SPEI values close to zero indicate conditions close to the average, positive values indicate abundant rains; negative values denote the drought periods. A meteorological drought in the period 2013-2018 is detected for the investigated area.

Figure 27. Tunisia: study area and location of the temperature and rain stations and monitoring wells

Table 3. Tunisia: station name and station code of the gauging stations

Station Name	Station code	Rain	Temp
Bezirk Dam	TUN002	X	
Beni Khalled Ferme	TUN005	X	
CTV Bouargoub	TUN006	X	
Grombalia DRE	TUN007	X	
CTV Menzel Bouzelfa	TUN008	X	
CTV Soliman	TUN009	X	
Nabeul	TUN010		X

Figure 28. Tunisia: SPEIs for time windows of 3, 6, 9, 12, 18, 24 and 36 months

The groundwater levels were collected from 23 wells in the period 2000-2020 (Figure 27 and Table 4); one or two data per year are available in the period 2000-2020. Figure 29 shows the observed GWLs data with their trend lines. There is not a uniform trend over the considered area; therefore, the analysis was performed at the specific local scale defined by the well locations.

Table 4. Tunisia: name and codes of the monitoring wells

Well Name	Well code	Well Name	Well code
12440	W1	8588	W13
6922	W2	13397	W14
2183	W3	12202	W15
2171	W4	13571	W16
2543	W5	8844	W17
2534	W6	2379	W18
1404	W7	12134	W19
2008	W8	12405	W20
2025	W9	12406	W21
11419	W10	12961	W22
13474	W11	13329	W23
8589	W12		

Regarding the quality data, three datasets are available (Table 5). The first, named official observation points, provide dry residuals and nitrate for 7 monitoring points and 11 sampling campaigns from 2009 to 2019. The second dataset, named InTheMED quality data, provide groundwater quality data for 20 monitoring points for a sampling campaign conducted in 2021. The third dataset provides similar information collected for 23 monitoring points and two sampling campaigns in 2000 and 2015. All these datasets have monitoring points at different locations. The last two dataset cannot be used as one or two campaigns are not enough to perform statistical analysis. Figure 30 shows the time series of nitrates provided by the first dataset with their regression lines. There is not a uniform trend over the investigated area. For some wells, the nitrates increase during the 10 considered years, otherwise for some wells a decreasing trend is noticed. The locations of the groundwater monitoring wells and nitrate monitoring wells is not the same; hence, it is not possible to relate nitrate and groundwater levels.

Figure 29. Tunisia: Groundwater levels (m a.s.l.) recorded in the period 2000-2020. The points are the observations and the solid line is the regression line

Table 5. Tunisia: datasets of quality data

Dataset	Variable	Monitoring points	Sampling campaigns	Time of record
Official points	Dry residue and nitrate	7	11	2009-2019
InTheMED Quality data	Na ⁺ , NH ₄ ⁺ , K ⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Na ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Cl ⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , PO ₄ ³⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻	20	1	2021
Slama et. al	Salinity, Na ⁺ , K ⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , Cl ⁻ , HCO ₃ ⁻	23	2	2000 and 2015

The exploitation data are available on the whole area collected every five years in the period 1980-2020 (Table 6). However, the dataset presents not enough data for accurate statistical analysis and the location of the exploitation wells is unknown.

For these reasons, the proposed surrogate model considered only the precipitation, temperature and groundwater level data.

Figure 30. Tunisia: Nitrate recorded in the period 2009-2019. The points are the observations and the solid line is the regression line.

Table 6. Tunisia: exploitation rate data

Years	Total number of wells	Number of abandoned wells	Estimated renewable resources (Mm ³ /year)	Exploitation (Mm ³ /year)
1980	5689	1032	--.--	53.8
1985	5733	1032	35.7	60.2
1990	8280	1529	35.5	89.7
1995	8430	1741	51.0	90.0
2000	8408	2041	51.0	93.0
2005	8531	2085	51.0	90.0
2010	8814	2085	51.0	104.6
2015	8814	1904	51.0	106.0
2020	8819	1904	51.0	106.0

Description of the Surrogate Model

A simple data-driven surrogate model has been developed to evaluate the impacts of climate change on groundwater levels (Secchi et al., 2021). A linear regression model has been used to describe the relationship between meteorological variables and groundwater levels (GWL). The first step for the development of the surrogate model is to investigate if the historical

rainfall and temperature data, in terms of SPEIs, and groundwater levels collected in monitoring wells are correlated. The meteorological indices and GWL data are defined correlated if the Pearson correlation coefficient is greater than 0.7.

For those wells presenting satisfactory correlation, a linear regression relationship has been computed between GWLs and SPEIs. This linear regression model represents the surrogate model that describes the dependence of groundwater levels on meteorological variables and will be used to evaluate the future groundwater levels based on future SPEI values, estimated by means of an ensemble of regional climate models (RCMs) under different climate scenarios (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5).

Evaluation of the Performance

The correlation between the GWLs of each well and SPEIs computed at the different time scales have been initially evaluated considering all the available data and then using only GWLs observed in February, March and April. The results are depicted in Figure 31. The Pearson correlation coefficients are very low if computed on all the available data for all wells. On the contrary, correlations increase for some wells if the analysis is computed on the period February-April. This stems for the fact that groundwater resources in these months presents minimal anthropogenic influence due to pumping and irrigation. The wells that do not show correlation for both analyses are likely affected by external factors and they do not respond to the meteorological variables only. Moreover, the results highlight a different sensitivity of the well data to the climate variables; the wells present the highest correlation at different time scale. The groundwater levels respond to the climate variables with different time lag probably due to the distinct characteristics of the aquifer and wells depths.

Therefore, the surrogate model has been developed based on late winter and early spring months data and considering the wells that present at least a Pearson correlation coefficient greater than 0.7, resulting in eight correlated wells. In Figure 32 to Figure 39, the results for all the eight correlated wells are shown; the linear regression models with their confidence interval are depicted.

For future projections (Task 3.4), the regression model calculated considering the SPEI at the time scale with the highest correlation will be used as surrogate model.

Figure 31. Tunisia: Pearson correlation coefficients between groundwater levels observed at the 23 wells (y-axis) and the and SPEIs at the time scale of 3, 6, 9, 12, 18, 24 and 36 months (x-axes) considering all months (a) and February-April months, respectively

Figure 32. Tunisia: linear regression model for the well 12440. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

Figure 33. Tunisia: linear regression model for the well 2183. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

Figure 34. Tunisia: linear regression model for the well 2171. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

Figure 35. Tunisia: linear regression model for the well 2543. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

Figure 36. Tunisia: linear regression model for the well 2008. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

Figure 37. Tunisia: linear regression model for the well 8844. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

Figure 38. Tunisia: linear regression model for the well 2379. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

Figure 39. Tunisia: linear regression model for the well 12405. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

2.5. Castro Verde (Portugal)

Objectives of the Surrogate Model

The objectives of the surrogate model for Castro Verde (Portugal) are the investigation of potential impacts of climate changes on groundwater availability. Also, for this study area, a complete numerical model is not available and a data-driven surrogate model has been developed based on groundwater levels, precipitation and temperature data. Assuming that the hydrological processes will not change over time, the proposed method is a statistical method that allows a fast evaluation of groundwater variations based on precipitation and temperature future scenarios.

Description of the Data

Castro Verde case study belongs to the Portuguese South Zone of Guadiana Basin groundwater mass, located in the south part of the Guadiana Hydrographic Basin (Figure 40).

Figure 40. Portugal: study area and locations of the meteorological and piezometric stations (SNIRH)

Both precipitation and temperature data were collected from 81 meteorological stations for an overall period between 1970-2021 (Figure 40 and Table 7). For most of the stations,

precipitation data are available on a daily basis, whether throughout the entire period or during a specific range of years. Regarding temperature data, only eleven stations present temperature measurements taken in a daily or monthly frequency, during distinct periods of time. Piezometric data were collected from 106 piezometric stations for an overall period between 1997-2022 (Figure 40 and Table 8). Most of the stations show measurements taken every other month or in a monthly frequency, each one during different periods of time.

Table 7. Portugal: name, code, and reference of the meteorological stations, as well as frequency of measurements, for an overall period between 1970-2021 (SNIRH)

Station Name	Station code	Reference	Precipitation (Frequency of measurements)	Temperature (Frequency of measurements)
ALANDROAL	21M/02UG	M1	Daily	None
ALBERNOA	26J/04UG	M2	Daily since 1979	None
ALBUFEIRA DE ODELEITE	30M/05F	M3	Daily from 2004 until 2008	Daily/monthly from 2001 until 2008
ALBUFEIRA DO ALQUEVA	24L/02F	M4	Daily from 2004 until 2007	Daily from 2002 until 2018
ALBUFEIRA DO ALQUEVA (MOURÃO)	22M/05F	M5	Daily from 2004 until 2007	Daily/monthly from 2002 until 2018
ALBUFEIRA DO ALQUEVA ILHA (EDIA)	24L/03C	M6	Daily from 2007 until 2009	None
ALBUFEIRA DO CAIA	19O/02F	M7	Daily from 2002 until 2010	Daily/monthly from 2001 until 2018
ALCARIA (CASTRO MARIM)	30L/04UG	M8	Daily	None
ALCARIA LONGA	28J/01G	M9	Daily	None
ALCOUTIM	29M/01UG	M10	Daily	None

Station Name	Station code	Reference	Precipitation (Frequency of measurements)	Temperature (Frequency of measurements)
ALEGRETE	18N/02G	M11	Daily since 1980	None
ALGODÔR	27K/01UG	M12	Daily since 1986	None
ALMODÔVAR	28I/01UG	M13	Daily	None
AMARELEJA	24N/01UG	M14	Daily	None
AMIEIRA	24L/01C	M15	Daily	Daily/monthly 1980-2000
ARRONCHES	19N/01UG	M16	Daily	None
AZARUJA	21K/01UG	M17	Daily	None
BARRAGEM DO BELICHE	30M/06G	M18	Daily since 2001	None
BARRAGEM DO CAIA	19O/02C	M19	Daily	Daily/monthly 1970-1998 and 2016-2017
BARRANCO DO VELHO	30J/01UG	M20	Daily	None
BARRANCOS	25P/01UG	M21	Daily	None
CAIA (MONTE CALDEIRAS)	20O/02UG	M22	Daily	None
CASTRO MARIM	30M/03UG	M23	Daily	None
CASTRO VERDE	27I/01G	M24	Daily	None
CATRAIA	30J/02G	M25	Daily until 1974	None
CORTE DA VELHA	27K/02UG	M26	Daily	None
CORTE PEQUENA	27J/02U	M27	Daily until 2000	None
CORTES PEREIRAS	29L/02U	M28	Daily from 1996 until 1999	None
CORUJOS	30L/01UG	M29	Daily	None
CUBA	24J/03UG	M30	Daily	None
DEGOLADOS	19O/03UG	M31	Daily since 1980	None

Station Name	Station code	Reference	Precipitation (Frequency of measurements)	Temperature (Frequency of measurements)
ESPERANÇA	19N/03UG	M32	Daily since 1980	None
FEITEIRA	30J/03G	M33	Daily since 2001	None
FERREIRA CAPELINS	22M/04UG	M34	Daily since 1980	None
FIGUEIRAIS	30M/01G	M35	Daily until 1984	None
FORO ESPANHOL	22M/02C	M36	Daily from 1980 until 1999	Daily/monthly 1980-1991
GIÕES	29K/02UG	M37	Daily since 1980	None
GUEDELHAS	29J/05UG	M38	Daily since 1979	None
HERDADE DE VALADA	26M/01C	M39	Daily	Daily/monthly 1970-1989 and 2000-2020
JUROMENHA	21N/01UG	M40	Daily	None
MALFRADES	29K/03UG	M41	Daily since 1980	None
MARTIM LONGO	29K/01C	M42	Daily	Daily/monthly 1989-2008
MERCADOR	30K/01UG	M43	Daily	None
MESQUITA	28L/02UG	M44	Daily since 1980	None
MONTE DA BRINJEIRA	29K/05G	M45	Daily from 2001 until 2017	None
MONTE DA TORRE	25M/03C	M46	Daily from 2001 until 2017	Daily/monthly 2001-2017
MONTOITO	22L/03UG	M48	Daily from 1980 until 2017	None
MURES ASSECA (TERRUGEM)	20M/04G	M49	Daily from 2001 until 2008 and from 2015 until 2017	None

Station Name	Station code	Reference	Precipitation (Frequency of measurements)	Temperature (Frequency of measurements)
MÉRTOLA	28L/01UG	M50	Daily	None
PEDROGÃO DO ALENTEJO	25L/01UG	M51	Daily	None
PENEDOS	29K/04UG	M52	Daily since 1980	None
PENILHOS	28J/02UG	M53	Daily 2001-2008 and 2014-2017	None
PEREIRO	29L/01UG	M54	Daily	None
PORTEL	24K/01UG	M55	Daily	None
REDONDO	22L/01U	M56	Daily until 1999	None
REGUENGOS	23L/01G	M57	Daily	None
ROSÁRIO (ALMODÔVAR)	28I/02U	M58	Daily 1983-2000	None
ROSÁRIO (CAPELINS)	22M/03UG	M59	Daily from 1980 until 2017	None
SALVADA	26K/01UG	M60	Daily	None
SANTA BARBARA DE PADRÕES	28J/03UG	M61	Daily from 1979 until 2017	None
SANTA CLARA DO LOUREDO	26J/03UG	M62	Daily from 1979 until 2017	None
SANTA CRUZ	29J/03UG	M63	Daily from 1980 until 2017	None
SANTA EULÁLIA	19N/02U	M64	Daily until 2000	None
SANTA IRIA	26L/02UG	M65	Daily from 1980 until 2017	None
SANTA SUSANA	22L/02UG	M66	Daily	None
SANTIAGO MAIOR	22M/01UG	M67	Daily	None
SANTO ALEIXO DA RESTAURAÇÃO	25O/01UG	M68	Daily	None

Station Name	Station code	Reference	Precipitation (Frequency of measurements)	Temperature (Frequency of measurements)
SAPAL DE ODELEITE (Ex. FONTE DO PENEDO)	29M/02UG	M69	Daily from 1992 until 1999	None
SERPA	26L/01UG	M70	Daily	None
SOBRAL DA ADIÇA	25N/01UG	M71	Daily from 1980 until 2017	None
SOBREIRA	30I/02UG	M72	Daily until 2017	None
SÃO JOÃO DOS CALDEIREIROS	28K/01UG	M73	Daily 1983-2010	None
SÃO JULIÃO	18N/01UG	M74	Daily since 1980	None
SÃO MANÇOS	23K/01UG	M75	Daily	None
SÃO MARCOS DA ATABOEIRA	27J/01UG	M76	Daily 1972-2010	None
TRINDADE	26J/01UG	M77	Daily	None
VALE DE CAMELOS	27J/03C	M78	Daily 1989-2016	Daily/monthly 1989-2016
VIDIGUEIRA	24K/02UG	M79	Daily until 2016	None
VILA VIÇOSA	21M/01UG	M80	Daily	None
ÁLAMO	28K/02UG	M81	Daily since 1980	None

Table 8. Portugal: Name, code, and reference of the piezometric stations, as well as frequency of measurements taken for an overall period between 1997-2022(SNIRH)

Station Name	Station code	Reference	Frequency of measurements
AC 8	532/136	P1	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002
AC1 - Monte da Vinha	428/36	P2	Monthly/every 2 months from 2004 until 2022
AC2 - Roças de Baixo	401/36	P3	Monthly/every 2 months from 2004 until 2022

Station Name	Station code	Reference	Frequency of measurements
Algaravenha	413/78	P4	Monthly/every 2 months from 1999 until 2007
Amada	428/17	P5	Monthly/every 2 months from 1998 until 2006
Atalaia	414/68	P6	Monthly/every 2 months from 1998 until 2004
BARRO BRANCO	426/302	P7	Monthly/every 2 months from 1997 until 2007
Barrancas	414/67	P8	Monthly/every 2 months from 1998 until 2022
CP 1	551/27	P9	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
CP 1/93	522/200	P10	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
CP2	532/211	P11	Monthly since 2021
Caia	414/71	P12	Monthly/every 2 months from 1998 until 2022
Campo	414/70	P13	Monthly/every 2 months from 1998 until 2007
Carrascal	426/348	P14	Monthly/every 2 months from 1997 until 2022
Ccanas	512/32	P15	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2022
Elvas	414/45	P16	Monthly/every 2 months from 1997 until 2007
FURO 2	559/21	P17	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
FURO DOS POMARES	512/212	P18	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
GARGALÃO	524/116	P19	Monthly/every 2 months from 2011 until 2022
JK 10	600/50	P20	Monthly/every 2 months from 1997 until 2022

Station Name	Station code	Reference	Frequency of measurements
JK 4 S09	600/44	P21	Monthly/every 2 months from 1997 until 2022
LF 4	533/51	P22	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
Monte Soares	427/24	P23	Monthly/every 2 months from 2003 until 2006
PFT 1	511/71	P24	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2003
PFT 1	542/19	P25	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
Pena Clara	399/12	P26	Monthly/every 2 months from 1998 until 2007
Poço Alamo-Cabida	471/81	P27	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço Barranco da Aldeia dos Testudos	522/253	P28	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço Horta dos Coentros	522/255	P29	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço Monte das Caldeiras	510/65	P30	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço de Pias	523/70	P31	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço em Caliços	533/74	P32	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço na Herdade Vale do Carvão	501/311	P33	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço na Herdade de Belmeque	524/114	P34	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço na Horta da Genoveva	531/46	P35	Few measurements between 2016 and 2017
Poço no Agueiro	512/215	P36	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017

Station Name	Station code	Reference	Frequency of measurements
Poço no Cangueiro	523/68	P37	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço no Monte Branco	512/211	P38	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço no Monte da Morena	510/68	P39	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço no Monte das Faias	471/82	P40	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço no Monte das Palmeiras	523/72	P41	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço no Monte de Magalhães	522/254	P42	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço no Monte do Lisboa	499/204	P43	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço no Monte do Louseiro	460/255	P44	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço no Monte do Moinho Branco	499/203	P45	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço no Monte do Outeiro	510/66	P46	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço no Monte dos Atafuis	499/202	P47	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
Poço nos Caliços	512/210	P48	Monthly/every 2 months from 2016 until 2017
RF 1	524/85	P49	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
SD3 Bicas1	501/63	P50	Monthly/every 2 months from 2001 until 2002
SDH1-VILA VIÇOSA	426/334	P51	Monthly/every 2 months from 1997 until 2022
SDH2 - RIO DE MOÍNHOS	426/335	P52	Monthly/every 2 months from 1997 until 2022

Station Name	Station code	Reference	Frequency of measurements
SDH3 - Monte da Lobata	532/75	P53	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2022
SDH4 - NORA	426/337	P54	Monthly/every 2 months from 1997 until 2022
SH LAMEIRA 1	513/34	P55	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2022
SH LAMEIRA 2	513/35	P56	Monthly/every 2 months from 2011 until 2022
SH MONTE BRANCO 1	512/50	P57	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2022
SH PALHAIS 2	524/49	P58	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2022
SH ROSA DA LAVADA 1	524/50	P59	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2022
SH SANTO ANTÓNIO 2	501/65	P60	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2022
SI1	533/43	P61	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2003
Salvador	387/4	P62	Monthly/every 2 months from 1999 until 2007
Sto António	413/123	P63	Monthly/every 2 months from 1997 until 2007
TCN1 - Vila Boim	413/54	P64	Monthly/every 2 months from 1997 until 2007
TS 1	532/153	P65	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
TS 3	524/82	P66	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
TS 4	524/83	P67	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002
Vale Vargo	524/51	P68	Monthly/every 2 months from 1997 until 2022

Station Name	Station code	Reference	Frequency of measurements
-	387/8	P69	Monthly/every 2 months from 2011 until 2022
-	399/6	P70	Monthly/every 2 months from 2010 until 2022
-	400/7	P71	Monthly/every 2 months from 1999 until 2020
-	414/116	P72	Monthly/every 2 months from 2008 until 2022
-	428/37	P73	Monthly/every 2 months from 2010 until 2022
-	441/10	P74	Monthly/every 2 months from 1997 until 1999
-	523/29	P75	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002
-	523/30	P76	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
-	523/31	P77	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002
-	523/32	P78	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2003
-	523/33	P79	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
-	523/36	P80	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
-	523/38	P81	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
-	523/40	P82	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
-	523/41	P83	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002
-	523/42	P84	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002

Station Name	Station code	Reference	Frequency of measurements
-	523/43	P85	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002
-	523/44	P86	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002
-	524/40	P87	Monthly/every 2 months from 2006 until 2007
-	524/60	P88	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2001
-	550/28	P89	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002
-	558/11	P90	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002
-	558/49	P91	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
-	558/52	P92	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002
-	558/53	P93	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
-	559/1	P94	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2004
-	559/17	P95	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002
-	559/25	P96	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002
-	567/11	P97	Monthly/every 2 months from 2000 until 2002
-	573/15	P98	Monthly/every 2 months from 1999 until 2022
-	581/41	P99	Monthly/every 2 months from 1999 until 2022
-	589/31	P100	Monthly/every 2 months from 1999 until 2015

Station Name	Station code	Reference	Frequency of measurements
-	591/62	P101	Monthly/every 2 months from 1999 until 2012
-	591/94	P102	Monthly/every 2 months from 2012 until 2022
-	598/143	P103	Single measurement in 1996
-	600/24	P104	Monthly/every 2 months from 2009 until 2022
-	600/266	P105	Monthly/every 2 months from 2015 until 2022
-	600/28	P106	Monthly/every 2 months from 2009 until 2015

Among the available monitoring well series, 37 wells were considered for their data abundance (Figure 41). We have selected wells that have at least 50 monthly records; Figure 42 shows the observed data with their trend lines. There is not a uniform trend over the considered area; therefore, the analysis was performed at the specific local scale defined by the well locations.

The precipitation and temperature data used in this analysis involve 17 rain gauges and 5 temperature stations selected for their data abundance in the period 1997-2021 (Figure 41). The gaps in the precipitation and temperature time series were filled using the FAO method (Allen et al., 1998). The data have been processed with the Thiessen polygon techniques to obtain precipitation and temperature areal averages.

The climate variables are investigated in terms of Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Indices (SPEIs) computed at different accumulation periods (1, 3, 6, 9, 12, 18, 24 and 36 months). The SPEI is a statistical index useful in detecting the meteorological droughts using monthly differences between precipitation and potential evapotranspiration; (Vicente-Serrano et al. 2010). Figure 43 reports the SPEI computed considering the precipitation and temperature data averaged over the area of interest. SPEI values close to zero indicate conditions close to the average, positive values indicate abundant rains; negative

values denote the drought periods. A meteorological drought period that starts in 2009 is detected for the last decade.

Figure 41. Portugal: study area and location of the selected temperature and rain stations and monitoring wells

Figure 42. Portugal: groundwater levels (m a.s.l.) recorded in the period 1997-2021. The points are the observations and the solid line is the regression line

Figure 43. Portugal: SPEIs for time windows of 1, 3, 6, 9, 12, 18, 24 and 36 months

Description of the Surrogate Model

A simple data-driven surrogate model has been developed to evaluate the impacts of climate change on groundwater levels (Secci et al., 2021). A linear regression model has been used to describe the relationship between meteorological variables and groundwater levels (GWL). The first step for the development of the surrogate model is to investigate if the historical

rainfall and temperature data, expressed in terms of SPEIs, and groundwater levels collected in monitoring wells are correlated. The meteorological indices and GWL data are defined correlated if the Pearson correlation coefficient is greater than 0.7.

For those wells presenting satisfactory correlation, a linear regression relationship has been computed between GWLs and SPEIs. This linear regression model represents the surrogate model that describes the dependence of groundwater levels on meteorological variables and will be used to evaluate the future groundwater levels based on future SPEI values, estimated by means of an ensemble of regional climate models (RCMs) under different climate scenarios (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5).

Evaluation of the Performance

The correlation between the GWLs of each well and SPEIs computed at the different time scales have been initially evaluated considering all the available data and then using only GWLs observed in February, March and April. The results are depicted in Figure 44. For wells that present less than 20 data in the considered period, the correlation coefficients were set equal to zero. The correlations increase for some wells if the analysis is computed on the period February-April. This stems for the fact that groundwater resources in these months presents minimal anthropogenic influence due to pumping and irrigation. The wells that do not show correlation for both analyses are likely affected by external factors and they do not respond to the meteorological variables only. The GWL data are correlated with SPEI at different time scale probably due to the distinct characteristics of the aquifer and wells depths. Most of the wells present the highest correlation with the largest time scale (36 months) denoting that groundwater levels respond to the climate variables with a large time lag. This is due to the presence of many dams and artificial lakes among which Alqueva Dam that creates the largest artificial lake in Europe. The reservoirs could have multi-year regulation that can mask the dependence from the natural hydrological cycles.

The surrogate model has been developed based on late winter and early spring months data and considering the wells that present at least a Pearson correlation coefficient greater than 0.7, resulting in six correlated wells. From Figure 45 to Figure 50, the results for the six correlated wells are shown; the linear regression models with their confidence interval are depicted.

For future projections (Task 3.4), the regression model calculated considering the SPEI at the time scale with the highest correlation will be used as surrogate model.

Figure 44. Portugal: Pearson correlation coefficients between groundwater levels observed at the 23 wells (y-axis) and the and SPEIs at the time scale of 1, 3, 6, 9, 12, 18, 24 and 36 months (x-axes) considering all months (left) and February-April months (right)

Figure 45. Portugal: linear regression model for the well 581/41. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

Figure 46. Portugal: linear regression model for the well 400/7. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

Figure 47. Portugal: linear regression model for the well 512/32. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

Figure 48. Portugal: linear regression model for the well 513/34. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

Figure 49. Portugal: linear regression model for the well 524/49. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

Figure 50. Portugal: linear regression model for the well 600/24. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes

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